

Airborne Internet with Common Login for All Devices

Antony Scaria

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
antonyscaria2022a@mca.ajce.in

Jinson Devis

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
jinsondevis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract- We live in a time of sophisticated technology and worldwide information exchange. Everyone must transmit and receive massive volumes of data. People nowadays want to feel connected. Because to broadband and wireless connectivity in homes and workplaces, users are kept wire-free and enjoy rapid and simple access. The challenge is providing a powerful, fast, and consistent connectivity network to individuals travelling in automobiles and even flights. In this article, we will look into airborne internet, a technology that deals with connection in aviation and aircrafts. The idea is to use all of the group network infrastructure and implementations to build a high-speed network that connects aircraft and ground. Nowadays, everyone has access to the internet. However, maintaining the connection and charging all of the gadgets takes money. Making it feasible for people to use the internet without a wired connection by flying over a large area in an aircraft. A shared login will also allow people to connect to the internet using a single connection. A provider can provide a connection, as well as a single login that the user can use to connect all of their devices.

Keywords:- Airborne internet , aircraft , area covered.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's environment, communication and information sharing are required at all times and in all locations. Everyone wants to be connected no matter where they travel or relocate. Because there is a vast amount of data being delivered in the form of enormous audio, video, image, and video files, the capacity to convey data swiftly is critical for keeping connected. Another improvement is the ability to stay connected while travelling, which makes use of broadband and wireless networks in homes and businesses, providing a clutter-free high-speed network infrastructure to users of various domains and ages. In this study, we analyse

connectivity and network architecture in aviation using a well-known technology, the Airborne Internet. The goal is to employ all of the ground

network's resources and infrastructure to build a high-speed network connecting ground equipment to aircraft. We also provide users with a single login that they can use across all devices. would allow people to access the internet from any device with a single connection.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Abdullah Numani;Syed Junaid Nawaz;Muhammad Awais Javed, Architecture and Routing Protocols for Airborne Internet Access 2018 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics - Asia (ICCE-Asia)
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III. MOTIVATION

We have a wifi connection at home, but when we're out and about, we use the internet via our sim provider, which is what inspired me to write this essay. If we are able to access the internet through our home's wifi connection, it will be quite beneficial and enable us to save money. For this, wireless internet connectivity is required, and mobile devices and other devices must be able to access the connection in our home.

IV. METHODOLOGY

- The major argument of this study article is that most individuals utilise broadband at home or at work. We access the internet using personal gadgets such as smartphones and tablets..
- A service provider assists us in using the internet. We must reload the package for continuing service, whether at work or at home, and we must do the same with our smartphone service provider.
- When internet access is provided by satellite, often known as "airborne internet," we may utilise the same internet connection across all devices by utilising a login provided by the service provider.
- We may connect to the internet by logging in often using a username and password supplied by the service provider.
- The High Altitude Long Operation (HALO) network is the key technological component of this. This network, which functions similarly to a satellite, provides internet access using high-altitude aeroplanes. The range of this aircraft will be between 4 and 8 square miles. The most major benefit is that we can keep using our existing equipment without needing to change them. The High Altitude Long Operation aircraft expands the wireless communication hierarchy by adding a new layer.hierarchy.
- A HALO aircraft will serve as the wireless broadband communication hub.

- Fixed wireless broadband is expected to have a total throughput of 10 to 20 Gbps.
- User transmission speeds of at least 1.5 Mbps.
- The plane has been meticulously built to carry up to 900 kg of weight.
- To establish contact above a remote city, a fleet of three aircraft cycles through shifts.
- The aircraft maintains altitudes between 51,100 and 60,000 feet.
- At Minimum Look Angles (MLA) of 20 degrees, the cone of commerce has a diameter of 100 km.
- It has a potential range of 2000–3000 square miles.
- Customer premises Equipment makes up the majority of the HALO network.
- Equipment for commercial spaces.
- The HALO Gate
- Network command centres

V. BUILD MODEL

We require a shared login to connect our gadgets to one another and, eventually, to the internet, allowing us to utilise all of our devices with the same home internet connection.

We may connect the device and link all devices to the page using a username and password issued by the service provider.

We establish a HALO network with the help of an aeroplane. The plane will fly in shifts so that customers can access the internet at all times.

We can link the antenna of the aircraft to the mobile tower. In the same way that we do now, we may link a mobile or personal device to a mobile tower. The user can then access the internet using the normal login site.

We offer a module with a dish and a modem

that can be used at home or in the workplace and can be connected wirelessly or by cable.

VI. RESULT

- How airborne internet works is depicted in the above diagram.
- The aircraft is used to build a HALO network, which is used to provide consumers with internet access.
- The name of this technology is angel technology. This is due to the plane's heavenly flight over the cities.
- With the help of a shared login, users can use the same connection for multiple devices in different locations.

VII. CONCLUSION

- Nowadays, maintaining a relationship is just as important as establishing one..
- Because it is costly to maintain a connection and charge multiple devices, this technology allows us to access the internet with just one connection.

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